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Value-Added Tax and the Nigerian Economy

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the macroeconomic implications of value-added tax (VAT) on economic growth in Nigeria, using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. Data for the study were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Development Indicators of the World Bank. The analysis covered the period from 1994 to 2023. The ARDL technique was employed for further analysis, and the null hypothesis was tested at the 5% level of significance. For the individual coefficients, the short-run results revealed the following: LVATR (0.016085), INTR (-0.002585), INF (0.000269), LPDI (0.053445), LFPR (0.023358), and GFCF (0.005519). The long-run results showed LVATR (0.168007), LPDI (0.558232), INF (0.002807), LFPR (0.519162), GFCF (-0.00179), and INTR (-0.029910). Evidence from the results indicated that VAT revenue and private domestic investment have a significant and positive impact on economic growth in both the short and long run, which aligns with a priori expectations. The study recommends that the government should make effective and appropriate use of VAT revenue to create jobs, thereby encouraging citizens to work, given that the labour force participation rate (LFPR) has a positive and significant impact on the economy. This would improve the general

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standard of living and increase citizens' income, thereby stimulating consumption. Furthermore, it recommends that interest rates should be regulated by the monetary authorities to enable borrowing at favourable rates for investment purposes.

Keywords: Value Added Tax, Tax, Taxation, Vatable person, Economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

In any economic system, government participation cannot be ignored. There are four basic economic responsibilities of the government to the nation: regulatory, allocative, distributive, and stabilisation roles. Through its stabilisation role, the government, at the macroeconomic level, uses fiscal, monetary, and other policy instruments to pursue fundamental national objectives such as inflation control, unemployment reduction, balance of payments stability, and economic growth.

In addition, the government performs two primary functions for its citizens. First, the safeguarding of lives and property. Second, the provision of public goods. One of the government's roles is to establish various sources of revenue generation apart from oil revenue in order to fulfil its responsibilities to both the nation and its citizens. Onwioduokit (2020) argues that the question of how to acquire, increase, allocate, and expand revenue constitutes a major issue in Nigerian society. Taxation is one of the instruments the government employs to influence income distribution. Hence, the government imposes taxes to generate revenue, and taxation has become a major source of revenue for the Nigerian government.

However, the attitude of many Nigerians towards tax payment has led to revenue loss, particularly from direct taxes, due to the practices of tax avoidance and evasion (Patrick, Anwese, and Kenneth, 2017). To address this challenge, the Federal Government introduced Value Added Tax (VAT) through Decree No. 102 of 1993, replacing the Sales Tax under Decree No. 7 of 1986. VAT is a consumption tax levied at each stage of the consumption chain and borne by the final consumer of the product or service (Oraka, Okegbe, and Ezejiofor, 2017). Initially, VAT was charged at a rate of 5% on the supply of VATable goods and services in Nigeria. The rate was later increased to 7.5% following the assent to the Finance Act 2019 by President Muhammadu Buhari, which took effect on 13th January 2020.

The enactment of the Finance Act 2019, signed by President Buhari on 13th January 2020, introduced several amendments to the VAT Act. The Finance Act 2020 amended 14 tax and fiscal legislations, including the VAT Act, and also created the Crisis

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Intervention Fund and the Unclaimed Trust Fund. Section 34 of the Finance Act 2020 increased the VAT rate from 5% to 7.5%, representing a 50% increase. “The changes obviously validate the Federal Government's commitment to align Nigerian tax laws with global best practices, creating conditions that provide an enabling environment for businesses to flourish” (Nwofia and Olafaju, 2021).

To enhance VAT revenue, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) introduced the computerisation of the VAT collection system, effective from 1st April 2020. The Automated VAT platform (VATrac) enables efficient collection and remittance of VAT on transactions in the wholesale and retail sectors, and facilitates direct auditing and reconciliation of VAT transactions (Obayomi, 2021). VATrac is the only approved platform for submitting VAT returns and paying VAT dues for the affected businesses. The FIRS mandated such businesses to contact the nearest tax office for onboarding onto VATrac. These businesses must include the following information in their sales receipts: FIRS Tax Identification Number (TIN) or Joint Tax Board TIN, printout date, goods/product description, receipt number, and the standard 7.5% VAT rate. Businesses with annual taxable supplies above ₦25 million are required to liaise with their local FIRS office to ensure compliance with VATrac and proper transaction documentation. These measures aim to increase VAT revenue by enforcing compliance, curtailing leakages, broadening the tax base, and reducing administrative costs (Obayomi, 2021).

Previously, non-resident persons were only required to register for VAT if they were conducting business in Nigeria. However, the new Section 10 of the VAT Act mandates all non-resident persons making taxable supplies of goods and services to Nigeria to register for VAT and obtain a TIN from FIRS. They must also include VAT on invoices for all taxable supplies and may appoint a representative for their tax obligations in Nigeria. The Finance Act 2020 also expanded the list of VAT-exempt goods and services, including essential food items and services rendered by microfinance banks. Educational services covering kindergarten and other levels of schooling were also exempted. Furthermore, Section 38 of the Finance Act 2020 exempts businesses with an annual turnover of less than ₦25 million (Nwofia and Olafaju, 2021).

Available statistics from the CBN Statistical Bulletin indicate that VAT has generated significant revenue since its inception. For instance, in the first half of 1994, it generated ₦13.67 billion—about 24% above the pro-rata revenue projection of ₦11 billion for that period (CBN, 2018). By the end of 1995, VAT revenue rose to ₦20.26

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billion. In 1996, the government estimated VAT revenue at ₦22 billion, with ₦7.01 billion earned in the first quarter alone. VAT is a tax to which all states and local government areas in the federation contribute. Efficient monthly revenue accounting by the FIRS has enabled the government to allocate VAT revenue to all state governments on a monthly basis. VAT revenue figures for 2010 to 2016 were ₦564.89 billion (2010), ₦659.16 billion (2011), ₦802.7 billion (2012 and 2013), ₦803 billion (2014), ₦767.3 billion (2015), and ₦828.2 billion (2016) (CBN Statistical Bulletin & FIRS Collection Profile, 2010–2016).

In 2018, the FIRS reported a total VAT collection of ₦1.1 trillion, out of the total ₦5.3 trillion it generated during the 2018 fiscal year, compared to ₦972.34 billion in 2017. The FIRS also announced a target of ₦3 trillion from VAT for 2019—an increase of over 200% from 2018 (CBN, 2018; Madugba and Azubuike, 2016; Andersen Tax Digest, 2019). Following the launch of the Strategic Revenue Growth Initiative in 2019, the FIRS positioned VAT as a core component of revenue generation. This aligns with Nigeria's tax policy, which advocates for increased tax revenue through indirect taxation. All VAT proceeds are deposited into the VAT pool account, which is distributed monthly among the federal, state (including the Federal Capital Territory), and local governments in the ratio of 15%, 50%, and 35%, respectively, based on derivation, population, and equality principles (Babatunde, 2016).

The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2024) reported consistent growth in VAT revenue, noting a 9.11% increase between Q1 and Q2 2024 and a 19.21% rise in Q1 2024 compared to Q4 2023. NBS (2024) therefore affirms that VAT remains a significant source of national revenue.

VAT revenue is typically injected into the economy through government consumption expenditure, which increases the general price level. Consequently, it is expected that total private consumption and output will decline, while total savings will rise. The argument here is that input VAT reduces product demand, depending on the elasticity of the product, indicating that consumers are not indifferent to price increases. Input VAT also raises production costs, leading producers to reduce output rather than lower prices. However, if the increased savings are reinvested in the economy through private investment, then employment, income, consumption, and output will increase.

Although VAT has substantially contributed to Nigeria's indirect tax revenue, its introduction aimed to accelerate economic growth and national development. However, in contrast to this objective, the country continues to experience infrastructure decay

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(Oraka, Ezejiofor, and Okegbe, 2017). In many parts of the country, citizens face poor power supply, inadequate healthcare, deteriorating infrastructure, unemployment, and low per capita income. These challenges have led to a declining standard of living and a rise in crime rates, insecurity, and threats to lives and property.

The persistence of these issues despite high VAT revenues prompted this study. Does VAT revenue actually end up in the VAT pool account or in the government treasury? Why has VAT revenue not alleviated these problems or guided the nation towards meaningful economic growth?

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

While the main objective of this study is to evaluate the macroeconomic implication of value-added tax for economic growth in Nigeria, the specific objectives are;

1. To examine the short-run and long-run impact of value added tax on the Nigeria economy.
2. To determine the relationship between VAT and the variables in the model.

CONCEPTUAL ISSUES

Value-Added Tax

Value-Added Tax (VAT) is a consumption tax paid at each stage of the consumption chain and borne by the final consumer of the product or service (Oraka et al., 2017). Therefore, VAT is an indirect tax levied in the course of spending, with the incidence falling on the final consumer of goods and services. It is essentially a goods and services tax. The concept of VAT originated with a French economist named Maurice Lauré and was initially referred to as *taxe sur la valeur* (Agbo and Nwadiolor, 2020).

Tax, on the other hand, is regarded as the social contract price between the governed and the government for the provision of social goods and services by the latter to the former (Okonkwo and Afolayan, 2019). For the purpose of this study, a tax is defined as a compulsory levy imposed by the government on the income of individuals and firms, as well as on goods and services, for a specified period, for which no direct benefits are received. Taxation, in turn, refers to the process or act of imposing such levies by the government or its agencies.

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Vatable Person

A Vatable person refers to a manufacturer, wholesaler, importer, or supplier of taxable goods and services. In this context, a taxable person is one who is registered under Section 8 of the VAT Decree. The effective operation of VAT since 1994 requires manufacturers, wholesalers, importers, and suppliers of vatable goods and services to register within six months of commencing business. Once registered, such a person is expected to charge and collect VAT on the goods and services supplied. The amount collected constitutes VAT output.

Conversely, purchasers of vatable goods and services are expected to pay VAT on those goods and services, referred to as VAT input. The difference between the VAT input and VAT output represents the amount payable to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). Babatunde (2016) argues that this amount is payable where the output VAT exceeds the input VAT; however, if the input VAT exceeds the output VAT, the excess may be claimed from the revenue authority.

THEORETICAL LITERATURE

The theoretical foundation of this study is based on the Ability-to-Pay Theory and the Theory of Increasing State Activity.

Ability-to-Pay Taxation Theory

This theory was propounded by Adam Smith in 1776. It supports the idea of a progressive income tax, positing that those with a greater ability to pay should contribute a higher percentage of their income (Utz, 2002). The theory further proposes that citizens should pay taxes in proportion to their individual capacity. It is widely regarded as a principle of equity and justice in taxation. For instance, Nigeria's Pay-As-You-Earn (PAYE) tax system is progressive in that it requires individuals with higher incomes to pay a greater proportion of their earnings in taxes. The core principles that justify the ability-to-pay theory include ownership of property, taxation based on expenditure, and income as the tax base.

Theory of Increasing State Activity

This theory was advanced by German economist Adolph Wagner in 1863, as presented in his classic work *Grundlegung der politischen Ökonomie*, where he formulated the Law of Increasing State Activity, commonly referred to as Wagner's Law. Wagner argued that there is a long-term tendency for government activity to expand as a country achieves higher levels of economic development (Laszlo and Bekzod, 2017). His

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perspective marked a shift from the earlier view that government involvement would decline as nations became wealthier. Wagner's position was supported by Musgrave and Musgrave (2004), who asserted that as countries industrialise, the public sector's share in the national economy grows persistently (Laszlo and Bekzod, 2017; Alan and Alex, 2000).

Empirical Literature

VAT has attracted the attention of numerous scholars and remains a subject of ongoing academic inquiry. This section reviews relevant empirical studies on the topic.

Madugba and Azubuike (2016) examined the relationship between VAT and economic development in Nigeria using time series data from 1994 to 2012 and employed multiple regression analysis. The results showed a negative and significant relationship between VAT and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The study recommended greater public education on the importance of VAT compliance. Omokhuale (2016) evaluated the contribution of VAT to Nigeria's economy between 2000 and 2012, revealing a strong and positive significant relationship between VAT and economic performance.

Okonkwo and Afolayan (2016) assessed VAT productivity through the cross elasticity of total consumption expenditure. Their findings showed that VAT productivity was not significant in relation to both total consumption expenditure (TCE^*/GDP) and private consumption expenditure ($TCE^*/VATable\ GDP$). Similarly, Oraka, Okegbe, and Ezejiofor (2017) investigated the effect of VAT on the Nigerian economy from 2003 to 2015. The study found a negative relationship between VAT and per capita income, but a positive relationship between VAT and government total revenue. It recommended that the Nigerian government implement fiscal policies to stimulate investment in agriculture, industry, and technology.

Nmesirionye, Jones, and Nwawuru (2018) explored the effect of VAT on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data from 1994 to 2012. The results indicated a negative but significant relationship between VAT and GDP in both the short and long run. The study advocated for infrastructure development to create private sector investment opportunities. Hammed, Irwan, Abidin, and Oluwaseyi (2018) also analysed the causal relationship between VAT and economic growth using ARDL techniques with data from 1980 to 2016. The findings revealed that VAT, domestic investment, and trade openness positively and significantly impacted real GDP. The study recommended addressing administrative inefficiencies to maximise VAT revenue.

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Efuntade (2020) examined the effect of VAT on revenue generation in Nigeria using the VECM method. The results indicated a positive and significant relationship. The study recommended improved accounting practices to enhance VAT efficiency. Rasaki, Rukayat, and Yusuf (2020) also examined the impact of VAT on economic growth using data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin. They conducted unit root tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller method and employed the Bounds test for co-integration. The findings showed that VAT had a positive and significant impact on economic growth in both the long and short run. The study recommended increasing the VAT rate and plugging revenue leakages.

Olakunbi, Omolara, and Oluwatosin (2022) investigated the contribution of VAT to total tax revenue in Nigeria using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The results indicated a negative and insignificant impact in both the short and long run. The authors recommended continued increases in the VAT rate.

Bakare (2023) studied the impact of VAT on output growth in Nigeria using the Ordinary Least Squares regression method. A positive and significant relationship was observed. The study advised that VAT revenue be channelled towards infrastructure development.

Oto and Wayas (2024) used descriptive statistics and simple regression analysis to assess the relationship between VAT and economic growth. Their findings showed a positive and significant relationship between VAT revenue and total government expenditure. The study recommended allocating a percentage of VAT revenue to finance critical sectors.

Iwegbe and Haruna (2024) examined the link between VAT and Nigeria's economic growth. Using descriptive statistics and simple regression on time series data from 1994 to 2022, the study found strong positive relationships between VAT and economic indicators. It concluded that GDP growth is a key driver of VAT revenue.

From the empirical review, several studies such as those by Rasaki, Rukayat, and Yusuf (2020); Oto and Wayas (2024); Iwegbe and Haruna (2024); and Hamed et al. (2018)—found a positive and significant relationship between VAT and economic growth. Conversely, other studies, including those by Oraka et al. (2017), Madugba and Azubuikwe (2016), Jones and Nwawuru (2018), and Olakunbi et al. (2022), reported a negative impact of VAT on economic growth.

However, the present study extends previous research by reflecting more current issues concerning VAT administration and economic development in Nigeria, making it a

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timely and commendable contribution to the existing body of knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts descriptive research design and time series analytical research design. The choice of this design is simply because of the nature of the study. Descriptive design helps to interpret past trend of events. It used time series data from 1994 to 2023 which was obtained from Central bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and World Bank development indicators of the World Bank.

Model Specification

To analyse the impact of VAT on economic growth in Nigeria, this study adopted a modified version of Olakunbi, Omolara and Oluwatosin (2022).

$$RGDP = F (VATR, PDI, INTR, INF, LFPR, GFCF) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

(1)

$$LRGDP = B_0 + \delta_1 LVATR + \delta_2 LPDI + \delta_3 INTR + \delta_4 INF + \delta_5 LFPR + \delta_6 GFCF + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

To capture the short-run and long-run estimates of ARDL model, Equation 2 is expressed in a dynamic form thus:

$$\Delta LRGDP_{t-1} = B_0 + \sum_{i=0} \delta_1 \Delta LVATR_{t-1} + \sum \delta_2 \Delta LPDI_{t-1} + \sum \delta_3 \Delta Int_{t-1} + \sum \delta_4 \Delta Inf_{t-1} + \sum \delta_5 \Delta LFPR_{t-1} + \sum \delta_6 \Delta GFCF_{t-1} + \mu_t \dots \dots (3)$$

A Priori expectation: $\delta_1 > 0; \delta_2 > 0; \delta_3 < 0; \delta_4 > 0; \delta_5 > 0; \delta_6 > 0;$

B_0 is the intercept or slope which measures the contribution to LRGDP with the effect of LVAT

$\delta_1 - \delta_4$ = The coefficient of the respective independent variables; t = The time period of observation; RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product Proxy for economic growth;

PDI = Private Domestic investment; VATR = VAT generated revenue;

INF = Inflation rate; INTR = Interest rate; LFPR = Labor force participation rate;

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GFCF = Gross fixed capital formation; LRGDP = Log of RGDP; LVATR= Log of VATR; LPDI = Log of PDI; μt = Error term

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Unit root test

The preliminary test that this study employed was the unit root test using the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillips Perron (Ph.P) tests. This study used it to test whether the variables were stationary or not. The result revealed that LVATR, INTR, and INF were stationary at level 1 (0). On the other hand, LFPR, GFCF, LRGDP, and LPDI were not stationary at level, so they were tested at first difference. Then they became stationary at first difference 1(1). In the Phillips-Perron test, the test revealed that LVATR, INTR, and INF were stationary at level 1(0), while LFPR, GFCF, LRGDP, and LPDI were tested at first difference 1(1), and they also became stationary. The result of the unit root test is presented in table 1 below. Since the series are stationary at 1(0) and 1(1), this breaks the use of ordinary least squares and gives room for the use of the ARDL technique for further analysis.

Table 1: Summary of Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillips Peron (Ph.p) Test

Variable	ADF.	Critical value 5 %	Order.	Ph.P.	5 % Critical	Order.
LRGDP	-5.507710	-3.612199	1(1)	-3.699973	-2.986225	1(1)
LVATR	-4.826653	-3.632896	1(0)	-3.849824	-2.981038	1(0)
LPDI	-4.749818	-3.603202	1(1)	-4.660477	-3.603202	1(1)
INTR	3.526120	-3.012363	1(0)	-5.881874	-3.595026	1(0)
INF	-3.322705	-2.981038	1(0)	-3.825644	-3.595026	1(0)
LFPR	-3.737365	-3.603202	1(1)	-5.173647	-3.612199	1(1)
GFCF	-4.381999	-3.603202	1(1)	-4.359756	-3.603202	1(1)

Source: Authors Computation 2025.

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Autoregressive distributed lag model

The study employed an autoregressive distributed lag model for estimation due to the result of the unit root test. The reason is provided by Perasan, Shin, and Smith (2001). The ARDL result is presented in Table 2 below. R² is 0.983058, which means that the independent variables were able to explain 98% of the variations in the dependent variable, while the remaining 2% was accounted for by variables not included in the model. The F-statistic was used to test for the significance of the model; it showed an F-stat. of 123.3029 has a p-value of 0.0000, which is significant at 5%. This confirms the goodness of fit of the variables. The Akaike information criterion from the result has the lowest value among the three models. This indicates that it is the best model to adopt. Therefore, the selected model gives a good description of the variables.

Table 2: Summary Of Auto Regressive Distributive Lag Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LRGDP(-1)	0.904260	0.201001	4.498785	0.0003
LVATR	0.016085	0.004408	3.649266	0.0020
LPDI	0.053445	0.097019	2.550877	0.0089
INF	0.000269	0.001030	0.261038	0.7972
LFPR	0.023358	0.008314	2.809454	0.0094
GFCF	0.005519	0.004709	1.172053	0.2573
GFCF(-1)	-0.005536	0.004261	-1.299415	0.2111
INTR	-0.002585	0.000745	3.470095	0.0043
C	-0.189570	1.015634	-2.186652	0.0041

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R-squared	0.983058	Mean dependent var	4.663350
Adjusted R-squared	0.975085	S.D. dependent var	0.272665
S.E. of regression	0.043038	Akaike info criterion	-3.186021
Sum squared resid	0.031489	Schwarz criterion	-2.750527
Log likelihood	50.41828	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.060615
F-statistic	123.3029	Durbin-Watson stat	2.008321
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Authors Computation 2025

Cointegrating result

The result of the individual coefficients as shown in Table 3 below reveals that in the short-run, LVATR is 0.016085, LPDI is 0.053445, INF is 0.000269, LFPR is 0.023358, GFCF is 0.005519, and INTR is -0.002585, while the long-run results reveal LVATR with a coefficient of 0.168007, LPDI 0.558232, INF 0.002807, LFPR 0.519162, GFCF -0.00179, and INTR -0.029910. From the cointegrating table, all the variables are positive and significant in the short-run except inflation and GFCF, which are positive and insignificant. Also, INTR is negative and has a significant impact. At the long-run, the variables showed the same sign as that of their short-run except GFCF, which showed a negative and insignificant impact against our a priori expectation.

The lagged value of the variables, which shows a linear combination of the dependent and independent variables, and the error correction mechanism denoted by ECM (-) showed the speed of adjustment to equilibrium. From the result, the ECM value is -0.495740, which is negative and significant. This implies that annually, 49% of inconsistencies in the short-run are corrected and incorporated into the long-run.

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Table 3: Summary Of Dynamic Form Long run and Short Run Relationship

Co-integrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(LVATR)	0.016085	0.004408	3.649266	0.0020
D(LPDI)	0.053445	0.097019	2.550877	0.0089
D(INF)	0.000269	0.001030	0.261038	0.7972
D(LFPR)	0.023358	0.008314	2.809454	0.0094
D(GFCF)	0.005519	0.004709	1.172053	0.0073
D(INTR)	-0.002585	0.000745	3.470095	0.0043
Co-intEq(-1)	-0.495740	0.201001	-2.476318	0.0099

Co-inteq = LRGDP - (0.1680*LVATR + 0.5582*LPDI + 0.0028*INF + 0.5192 *LFPR - 0.0002*GFCF - 0.0299*INTR -1.9800)

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LVATR	0.168007	0.346855	3.484371	0.0343
LPDI	0.558232	0.448516	2.544620	0.0202
INF	0.002807	0.008447	0.332304	0.7437
LFPR	0.519162	0.224435	2.313197	0.0079
GFCF	-0.000179	0.034619	-0.005173	0.9959
INTR	-0.029910	0.008751	3.417921	0.0012
C	-1.980048	14.574645	-0.135856	0.8935

Source: Authors Computation 2025

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ARDL bounds test result

ARDL bounds test result in Table 4 below shows the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables at 5 % level of significance. This is because the F-statistics of 4.786583 is above the upper bounds of 3.61. Therefore, using the 5 % level of significance, the study concludes that there exists a long-run relationship among the variables

Table 4: ARDL Bounds Test

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	4.786583	6

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.12	3.23
5%	2.45	3.61
2.5%	2.75	3.99
1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Authors Computation 2025.

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Findings

For the individual coefficients, the short-run result revealed LVATR of 0.016085, INTR of -0.002585, INF of 0.000269, LPDI of 0.053445, LFPR of 0.023358, and GFCF of 0.005519, while the long-run results revealed LVATR with a coefficient of 0.168007, LPDI of 0.558232, INF of 0.002807, LFPR of 0.519162, GFCF of -0.00179, and INTR of -0.029910. LVAT revenue and private domestic investment both have significant and positive impacts on economic growth in both the short-run and long-run which is in line with the a priori expectation. LFPR has a positive and significant impact on the economy. Interest rate has a negative and significant effect on economic growth both in the short-run and long-run. Inflation has a positive and insignificant impact on economic growth. GFCF has a positive and insignificant impact on the economy, though in the long-run, it has a negative impact against the a priori expectation.

DISCUSSION/IMPLICATION OF THE FINDINGS

The result of the short-run dynamic presented in Table 3 above revealed that LVAT revenue has a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Also, private domestic investment showed a significant and positive impact on economic growth. This implies that a 1% increase in LVAT revenue will increase economic growth by 1% also. If private domestic investment is increased by 1%, the economy will grow by 5%, and vice versa. The result of the interest rate shows that it has a negative and significant impact on the economy with a coefficient of -0.002585. The policy implication is for the monetary authorities to control the rise in interest rates because it might discourage borrowing and subsequent investment, which will be an impediment to the growth of the economy.

From the long-run result in table 3 above, the result is almost the same. LVATR with a coefficient of 0.168007 is significant and has a positive relationship with economic growth. Also, LPDI with 0.558232 has the same positive and significant relationship with LRGDP. This means that in the long-run, a 1% increase in LVAT and LPDI will result in a 16% and 55% increase in economic growth; hence, policymakers should encourage private investment. The interest rate is still negative with a coefficient of -0.029910 and significant in the long-run. The inflation coefficient of 0.002807 is positive and insignificant in the long-run. LFPR with a coefficient of 0.0519162 has a positive and significant impact on the economy; thus, the government should encourage labour participation by creating jobs. Also, the long-run coefficient of GFCF is -0.000179; it is negative and has an insignificant impact on the economy. This is not in line with the a priori expectation.

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This study tried to investigate the macroeconomic implication of value-added tax on the economy. In another way, it tried to know if value-added tax revenue has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. This was tested using the individual coefficients, their 't' statistics, and P-values for the significance of the various variables, while f-statistics were used to test for the overall significance of the model. Thus the model was significant at the 5% level of significance, as proved by the ARDL result. The result of this study proved that VAT revenue has a positive and significant impact on the economy both at the short run and in the long run.

VATR with a long-run coefficient of 0.168007 is positive and statistically significant, which means that if VAT revenue is increased by 1%, the economy will grow by 16%. This result shows that VAT has a long-run positive effect on the Nigerian economy; therefore, the government should favour policies that will encourage consumption since VAT is a consumption tax. The finding that VAT revenue has a positive and significant impact on economic growth is in line with the findings of Rasaki, Rukayat, and Yusuf (2020); Omokhualé (2016); Hammed et al. (2018); and Oto and Wayas (2024).

Conclusion

Evidence from this study proved that VAT revenue has a significant and positive impact on the Nigerian economy both in the short run and long run. The implication of this is that economic growth can be accelerated through an increase in VAT revenue. Therefore, the government should embark on economic policies and programs that will encourage both consumption and investment expenditures in the nation since VAT is a consumption tax. VAT is in line with the ability to pay theory, which allows consumers to make purchases and pay for VAT without necessarily knowing. If there is an increase in aggregate consumption expenditure, VAT revenue will increase. Then, if the VAT revenue is properly utilised and injected into the economy through public expenditure on programs like job creation and other empowerment programs as proposed by Wagner's theory of increasing state activities. This will improve the economic welfare of citizens.

Also, the monetary authorities should control the interest rate so that it will be favourable for investors to borrow since evidence from our results proved that domestic private investment is essential for the growth of the economy. If there is an increase in investment, employment will be created for citizens and output will increase. This will equally increase citizens' income, thereby increasing demand, and the multiplier effect

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will generally bring an increase in economic activities, which channels the nation towards economic growth.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should make effective and appropriate use of VAT revenue to create employment opportunities, thereby encouraging citizens to participate in the labour force, given that the labour force participation rate (LFPR) has a positive and significant impact on the economy. This will improve the general standard of living and increase household income, thereby stimulating consumption.
2. Interest rates should be regulated by the monetary authorities to enable citizens to borrow at favourable rates for investment purposes. Also, the government should facilitate easier access to credit.
3. The government should increase public awareness of the importance of VAT and address the loopholes in VAT collection, as this study has shown that VAT contributes significantly to government revenue.

Accordingly, this study recommends further research to examine the impact of VAT on trade openness and unemployment in Nigeria.

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